

Recommended citation: Zalewski, D. (2020). Curriculum Through the Market Lens - Mining Vacancy Data for Future-Proof Engineering Education. In van der Veen, J., van Hattum-Janssen, N., Järvinen, H.-M., de Laet, T., & ten Dam, I. (Eds.), *Engaging Engineering Education. SEFI 48th Annual Conference* (pp. 552-562). European Society for Engineering Education (SEFI), Enschede, The Netherlands. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14653953.

CURRICULUM THROUGH THE MARKET LENS – MINING VACANCY DATA FOR FUTURE-PROOF ENGINEERING EDUCATION

D.R. Zalewski¹

Saxion University of Applied Sciences
Enschede, The Netherlands

Conference Key Areas: *Future engineering skills, HE & Business, Career support*
Keywords: *curriculum, labor market, career*

ABSTRACT

Curricular design presents a constant challenge in engineering education amid the ongoing technological revolution. In fast-moving disciplines like computer or software engineering, a mismatch between the curriculum and market demands can develop rapidly over the course of years. Failure of an engineering program to match market requirements can lead to decreased students' satisfaction and, consequently, to dropping acquisition and retention rates.

Traditionally, the level of the curriculum coverage is benchmarked with alumni and company surveys. Both of these approaches incur financial costs, have poor response rates and suffer from intrinsic biases. Here, we present an alternative market analysis method and show how it can be used to aid curricular design. The method uses information scraped from job advertisement aggregators and employs data mining to discover current market demands.

This process is automated in a software tool. The tool employs search criteria and filters to download vacancies targeted at starting engineering professionals. The bodies of the advertisements are subsequently processed using text transformation and mining techniques to collect importance-weighted terms falling under one of the three categories: tools, techniques and concepts. Finally, the processed data is augmented with geographical information to enable geospatial analysis and visualization.

We demonstrate the usage of this method on a bachelor curriculum of an embedded software engineering program in the Netherlands. We show how the results of the job market analysis help discover courses with low relevance, at the same time highlighting curricular underrepresentation of some highly sought-after skills.

¹ *Corresponding Author*
D.R. Zalewski
d.r.zalewski@saxion.nl

1 INTRODUCTION

The European labor market has been undergoing a steady growth with the number of unfilled posts increasing by almost 50% in the past five years as measured with the *job vacancy rate* indicator [1]. This process is amplified in the ICT industry, which experiences very rapid employment development [2]. In the Netherlands the situation on the ICT labor market is the worst among all the professions; employers in this sector report that 70% of the vacancies are difficult to fill in. Notably, positions targeted at graduates of tertiary education programs account for 78% of the openings. Often, knowledge of specific programming languages or techniques is required, which further aggravates difficulties with finding a fitting candidate [3]. Given this situation, ensuring that ICT graduates have mastered the skills and knowledge that match the market demands not only increases their chances to find a job but also helps to alleviate the problem of understaffing. Well-prepared starting employees need less internal training shortening the time to reach full work efficiency.

Curricular design that closes the gap between ICT students' competences and industrial needs poses a persistent challenge. Some educational institutions approach it by following established curricular guidelines that are updated every few years by panels of international industrial and academic experts [4]. Others employ alumni surveys to measure the discrepancy between teaching practices and perceived importance of knowledge and skills in professional settings [5]. Both of those methods incur financial costs and suffer from intrinsic biases; composition of panels or survey audience strongly affects the outcomes. Moreover, both approaches have intentionally broad scope. Curricular guidelines have word-wide reach and are presented in a way that makes them adaptable to local circumstances, yet they lack details. Similarly, alumni studies recruit respondents across multiple industries and specializations to collect responses that guarantee sufficient statistical power [6]. Consequently, they identify mostly high level features like *design* or *quality* [7] that need to be subsequently translated into concrete curricular items. University programs faced with redesigning or adjusting their curricula struggle with adapting those guidelines and survey outcomes, relying on the expertise and personal preferences of their teaching staff.

Recently, another approach to discovery of qualifications expected from perspective ICT employees has been demonstrated. It applies topic modelling to a dataset of publicly available vacancy advertisements, to compose a throughout overview of job roles together with corresponding knowledge and skills [8]. We propose to extend this idea by applying data extraction techniques instead of performing exploratory analysis on a vacancy dataset. This way, more detailed market information can be obtained, leading to cataloging industry requirements relevant to a specific study program.

In this article, we describe this method, showing the collection and preparation steps necessary to create a vacancy dataset that is limited geographically, bound to a study profile and restricted in scope to postings relevant to junior employees. We

follow by describing data extraction based on keyword matching and analysis that results in a detailed snapshot of industry demands specific to a particular educational program's offering that can be readily applied as a base for curricular (re-)design. We show how this method is used to extract market requirements relevant to a program of *embedded software engineering* in the Netherlands and how this information was used to start an ongoing curriculum redesign.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 Data collection and pre-processing

Jobs are posted daily to numerous websites. To get the best possible representation of the market we used *Indeed*, a website that's a vacancy posting aggregator as a data source. Queries submitted to *Indeed* can contain phrases and use Boolean operators, which allows for composing complex requests. Moreover, the queries are always limited geographically by providing the target location and the search radius with a maximum of 100 km. The postings found on *Indeed* contain, next to the body of an advertisement, a unique identifier, a job's title, a company's name, a date of placement and a geographical location either as a city name or a postal code. This allows for post-collection filtering of data and focusing on a specific region or filtering out advertisements for senior positions.

We constructed the dataset by querying the vacancy website for 8 distinct geographical locations, making sure that the search areas overlapped and covered the whole country. For each location we used 7 search queries, relevant to the *embedded software engineering* program, such as: *embedded AND software*, *embedded AND engineering*, *embedded AND programming* and their local-language equivalents. One of the queries was a phrase containing the explicit study program name. *Indeed* uses a full-text search, guaranteeing that most of the postings related to the study program at hand were found. While gathering the data, only advertisements with the unique identifiers not yet present in the dataset were downloaded. Next, the text duplicates were removed using cosine similarity score calculated on *term frequency – inverse document frequency* embeddings of the 250 first words of each posting.

The remaining vacancies were filtered in a three-stage process that consisted of:

- 1) Removing advertisements belonging to known companies that specialize in internship recruitment only.
- 2) Removing entries based on keywords present in titles; in this step vacancies that addressed *senior*, *experienced*, *principal*, *leader*, *manager*, *internship*, and other non-relevant functions were dropped. In total there were 46 different direct match filters used in this step.
- 3) Removing advertisements that contained a requirement of more than four years' experience in the text based on regular expression matches.

Once the vacancies were collected, the following text transformations were applied to their bodies before performing any further steps:

- 1) Unicode codepoints replacement, for instance both \u00b5controller and \u03bccontroller were replaced with *microcontroller* (\u00b5 and \u03bc are the Unicode codepoints for the Greek character μ)
- 2) Known equivalent notation replacement, for instance both *ucontroller* and *micro-controller* was replaced with *microcontroller*.
- 3) Global synonym replacement – some words occur very infrequently in the dataset but can be replaced with a more general term, for instance both *Pic* and *Atmega* were replaced with *microcontroller* (*Pic* and *Atmega* are microcontroller families).

Subsequently, the geographical locations of the advertisements were encoded into longitude and latitude using geographical database lookup.

2.2 Feature extraction

2.2.1 Keywords counting

Advertisements targeted at ITC professionals are usually very specific and contain well-defined required skills' sets. For that reason, keyword counting with importance weighting was used for extracting the features from the vacancies. The bank of pre-defined keywords consisted of terms related to skills and knowledge items, grouped under three categories:

- 1) *Languages*, this category held programming languages, e.g.: *C++*, *Java*, *Python*.
- 2) *Techniques*, this category grouped keywords related to skills that usually can be taught during a single, semester-long course, e.g. *databases*, *Linux*, *Bluetooth*.
- 3) *Concepts*, this category contained terms that describe high-level concepts for which familiarity with multiple techniques is often necessary, e.g.: *testing*, *machine learning*, *agile*.

At this stage, advertisements that contained no matching keywords were removed from further analysis. For the remaining vacancies, both the occurrence of a keyword and the order of its appearance in the advertisement text was recorded. Based on this data a simple weighting scheme was applied for counting the keywords across the whole dataset. First, the following statistics were calculated for the number of unique keywords found per advertisement: the median (M) and the interquartile range (IQR). Subsequently, two boundaries were defined:

$$\begin{cases} FC = M + \frac{IQR}{2} \\ NC = M + 2 \cdot IQR \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

The FC boundary is the 75 percentile of the keyword counts per advertisement distribution, whereas NC sets up a limit of the normal observations – advertisements containing more or equal than NC keywords are outliers in the dataset.

$$c(i) = \begin{cases} 1, & i \leq FC \\ \frac{NC-i}{NC-FC}, & FC < i \leq NC \\ 0, & i > NC \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The weighting scheme was used as follows (Eq. 2): if a keyword appeared among the first FC keywords in a vacancy description it was counted as one. A keyword appearing after the first FC keywords but before the first NC keywords was counted using a linear scale going from one for FC to zero for NC. Keywords that appeared after the first NC keywords in a text were not counted. The application of weighting was meant to counteract the practice used by some agencies and employers of putting multiple, often non-relevant terms in an advertisement with the hope of getting more search hits. After processing each vacancy, the counts obtained this way were summed up across the whole dataset, producing an overall count for each keyword, c_k .

2.2.2 Data analysis

The keyword counts were used to derive two quantities: the keyword frequency (f_k) and the keyword proportion (p_k). The keyword frequency is the occurrence count of a keyword divided by the total number of job advertisements (Eq. 3). The keyword proportion is the fraction of the occurrence count of a keyword and the sum of all the keywords' counts (Eq. 4).

$$f_k = \frac{c_k}{N} \quad (3)$$

$$p_k = \frac{c_k}{\sum_i c_i} \quad (4)$$

While, keyword frequencies make it straightforward to gauge which skills are in high demand, keyword proportions can be used when assessing the curriculum coverage of a study program.

2.2.3 Curricular coverage

A keyword proportion (p_k) represents the share of market demand of a knowledge item associated with a keyword. As such it can be compared with the corresponding study load share expressed as the fraction of the ECTS points allocated to learning related content. When there is a match between the market demand share and the study load share, one can conclude that the curricular coverage of the related skill or knowledge item is adequate. Otherwise there is either under- or overrepresentation of a topic in the curriculum. To calculate the approximate study load of each knowledge item in a curriculum, the learning objectives of all the courses in the study program were analyzed and linked to knowledge and skill items. Next, a fraction of the ECTS points of a course was assigned to an associated keyword. For instance, for a semester-long, 6 ECTS course in operating systems

that teaches OS concepts using Linux but also offers practice in writing drivers and tools for this system, 2.4 ECTS might be allocated to learning Linux, while the remainder would go to advance practice in the C programming language.

To assess the curricular coverage, the ratio R_k between the study load share and the market demand share was calculated. If the ratio for a knowledge item was between 0.5 and 2.0, the curricular coverage was considered adequate within the limits of this study². Consequently, for R_k lower than 0.5 the curricular coverage was inadequate, while for R_k greater than 2.0 an item was judged to be overrepresented in the curriculum.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Data collection and market requirements

In total 2530 advertisements with unique identifiers were found and downloaded. After subsequent filtering steps this count was reduced to 866 unique vacancies targeted at young professionals with *embedded software engineering* background. The exact counts of items dropped at each filtering step can be found in Table 1. The five most common terms occurring in vacancies' titles that resulted in their removal were: *internship* (393 matches), *graduation assignment* (213) *senior* (132) *architect* (68) and *lead* (53). In the phrase filtering phase most vacancies (21) were excluded because they contained the requirement of "5 years of experience".

Table 1. Vacancy counts after subsequent filtering steps.

Procedure	Count removed	Count left
Vacancy scraping	---	2530
Title filtering	1148	1382
Internship companies	369	1013
Phrase filtering	33	980
Duplicate removal	66	914
No keywords found ³	48	866

The locations of the vacancies were not evenly geographically distributed (see Figure 1), the north-east part of the country received particularly few hits, despite the presence of a vocational university that offers an *embedded software engineering* program in this area.

There were 4550 keywords found among the whole dataset with a mean of 5.25 keywords per advertisement (stdev=3.1). The median keywords count per advertisement was 5 with the IQR of 4. Consequently, when counting the keywords

² Those limits, corresponding to "the market requirements are two times greater" and "the curricular coverage is two times too big" were chosen arbitrarily.

³ This step was performed only after feature extraction.

for further analysis, those that appeared after the 13th place ($M + 2 \cdot IQR$) in the body of an advertisement were skipped.

Figure 1. Geographic distribution of the vacancies. Schools that offer Embedded Software Engineering as a primary study program are marked with ■ (research universities) and with ▲ (vocational universities).

In Table 2 the first 15 most frequently occurring keywords in each of the three categories are listed. The most sought after programming languages are C and C++ (belonging to a group of systems programming languages), which contrasts with the results of other surveys where languages like Java and Python are usually in the lead [9]. This is the consequence of the strong presence of embedded and system development positions among the advertisements.

Table 2. The 15 most frequent keywords in Languages, Concepts and Techniques categories. (f_k – keyword frequency; p_k – keyword proportion).

Languages			Concepts			Techniques		
Keyword	f_k [%]	p_k [%]	Keyword	f_k [%]	p_k [%]	Keyword	f_k [%]	p_k [%]
c++	41.9	8.2	agile	25.5	5.0	linux	22.0	4.3
c	37.4	7.3	testing	21.0	4.1	databases	17.7	3.4
c#	20.9	4.1	scrum	20.8	4.1	real-time	16.0	3.1
java	16.8	3.3	electronics	17.2	3.3	plc	13.5	2.6
python	16.6	3.2	mechatronics	11.9	2.3	networking	13.4	2.6
js	10.2	2.0	oop	11.7	2.3	sql	11.4	2.2

Languages			Concepts			Techniques		
Keyword	f_k [%]	p_k [%]	Keyword	f_k [%]	p_k [%]	Keyword	f_k [%]	p_k [%]
html	9.8	1.9	cloud comp.	10.8	2.1	uml	9.4	1.8
matlab	6.0	1.2	vcs	10.0	1.9	ucontrollers	7.2	1.4
php	3.5	0.7	ci	9.2	1.8	iot	6.5	1.3
simulink	2.5	0.5	robotics	7.7	1.5	fpga	3.8	0.7
assembler	2.2	0.4	algorithms	6.8	1.3	scada	3.8	0.7
vhdl	2.1	0.4	math	6.5	1.3	arm	3.8	0.7
labview	2.0	0.4	machine learning	5.4	1.1	ethernet	2.5	0.5
delphi	1.5	0.3	control systems	3.0	0.6	embedded protocols	2.4	0.5
visual basic	1.3	0.2	machine vision	3.0	0.6	bluetooth	2.0	0.4

In the *Concepts* category, besides terms associated with the software engineering practice like *agile*, *scrum*, *testing* and *version control systems (vcs)* there are terms that can be linked to hardware development (*electronics*, *mechatronics*, *robotics*, *control systems*) but also skills that require mathematical background (*algorithms*, *machine learning* and simply *mathematics*). The appearance of the latter group may be related to the fact that many traditional *software engineering* programs in the Netherlands dropped mathematics altogether from their curricula, however, it is still taught during a standard *embedded software engineering* course. Employers know about it and seek *ESE* graduates for positions that require mathematical competences.

The keywords appearing under *Techniques* are mostly related to embedded development, besides *databases* and *sql (Structured Query Language, a language used only with databases)*. The reason for the strong presence of those two is perhaps the same as for *cloud computing* in *Concepts*; the emergence of Internet-of-Things and connected embedded devices that routinely communicate with cloud services and store their data in online databases.

3.2 Curriculum coverage

In Table 3 the results of the curricular coverage analysis for the assessed *embedded computer engineering* program are shown. Only items that had at least 1 % market demand share (p_k) are listed, unless they were represented in the curriculum. The items are sorted in the ascending R_k order (from the most underrepresented to the most overrepresented).

Table 3. Comparison of keyword proportions (p_k) and ECTS shares (p_{ECTS}) in the analyzed curriculum. The ration R_k between p_{ECTS} and p_k is considered within norm if it falls within the 0.5 – 2.0 interval.

	Keyword	p_k [%]	ECTS [-]	p_{ECTS} [%]	R_k [-]
underrepresented	c#	4.1	0	0	0
	real-time	3.1	0	0	0
	plc	2.6	0	0	0
	mechatronics	2.3	0	0	0
	cloud	2.1	0	0	0
	ci	1.8	0	0	0
	robotics	1.5	0	0	0
	machine learning	1.1	0	0	0
	python	3.3	0.8	0.7	0.2
	agile	5.0	1.8	1.6	0.3
	oop	2.3	0.9	0.8	0.3
	c++	8.2	3.6	3.2	0.4
	testing	4.1	1.8	1.6	0.4
	linux	4.3	2.1	1.9	0.4
adequate	databases	3.4	2.4	2.1	0.6
	vcs	1.9	1.8	1.6	0.8
	matlab	1.2	1.2	1.1	0.9
	networking	2.6	3.0	2.7	1.0
	uml	1.8	2.4	2.1	1.2
	assembler	0.4	0.6	0.5	1.3
	algorithms	1.3	2.4	2.1	1.6
	iot	1.3	2.5	2.2	1.8
	java	3.2	7.2	6.4	2.0
overrepresented	c	7.3	21.8	19.5	2.7
	microcontrollers	1.4	5.5	4.9	3.5
	fpga	0.7	3.0	2.7	3.6
	build systems	0.4	1.8	1.6	4.3
	control systems	0.6	3.0	2.7	4.6
	electronics	3.3	24.1	21.5	6.4
	math	1.3	15.3	13.7	10.7
	dsp	0.2	3.0	2.7	17.0

Moreover, *scrum* and *sql*, were skipped in this listing, as they always appear with respectively *agile* and *databases* in the advertisements and are also taught together.

Remarkably, only 9 out of the 23 skills / knowledge items seem to be represented in the curriculum in a proportion that's close to the labor market needs. When looking at the overrepresented items, *digital signal processing (dsp)*, *control systems* and *field programmable gate-arrays (fpga)* all have less than 1 % market demand share, while being taught in a dedicated 3 ECTS course each. *Mathematics* and *electronics* also seem to be taught too much, however, at least in the case of mathematical skills an argument can be made that they form the basis for other courses and are rarely mentioned directly in the advertisements because most employers assume knowledge of college level mathematics in university graduates.

Even more striking is the list with items that are not a part of the curriculum but there is a substantial market demand for them. *Real-time system*, *programmable logic controllers (plc)*, *mechatronics* and *cloud computing* all seem to deserve a place in the study program – the market demand share for them corresponds to around 12 ECTS study load.

There is also a mismatch between what programming languages the employers seem to require and what the curriculum offers. For systems programming, the demand for C++ is somewhat greater than for C, yet in the curriculum those proportion is completely reversed, only 3.6 ECTS are allocated to learning C++, while 22 ECTS go to teaching and practicing C. The market requirements shouldn't be surprising, considering the ubiquitous presence of high-level microcontrollers, that are usually programmed with C++, in embedded system nowadays. A similar observation can be made for Java and C# programming languages. The labor market clearly prefers C#, whereas the analyzed study program teaches the former.

Overall, there seem to be a remarkable discrepancy between the composition of the curriculum and the market needs.

3.3 Curricular re-design

In light of the findings presented in this study, the first steps were made to align the analyzed study program curriculum with the market demands. Since the scope of the redesign is big and concerns all the study years, in the beginning the courses of the first program year have been changed. Electronics courses worth 6 ECTS were removed from the curriculum. Those study points went into strengthening the underrepresented software engineering skills: *cloud computing*, *testing* and *object-oriented programming design (oop)*. Moreover, the balance between the programming languages taught was adjusted by promoting C++ to the main teaching language and, consequently, changing the language from C to C++ in some courses. Additionally, Java courses were replaced by a mix of C# and Python modules.

The curriculum will undergo further transformations, after the modifications in first-year courses will have finished. The focus will shift to the advanced curricular items, like replacing *digital signal processing (dsp)*, *control systems* and *field programmable*

gate-arrays (fpga) with more demanded real-time system, programmable logic controllers (plc), continuous integration (ci) and machine learning.

REFERENCES

- [1] Job vacancy statistics - Statistics Explained. https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Job_vacancy_statistics (accessed Apr. 09, 2020).
- [2] Mas M. *et al.*, The 2019 PREDICT Key Facts Report. An Analysis of ICT R&D in the EU and Beyond, 2019, p. 116987, doi: 10.2760/06479.
- [3] de Wit J. and Kalkhoven F., Factsheet Arbeidsmarkt ICT-beroepen, 2019. [Online]. Available: <https://www.uwv.nl/overuwv/kennis-cijfers-en-onderzoek/arbeidsmarktinformatie/factsheet-arbeidsmarkt-ict-2019.aspx>.
- [4] The Joint Task Force on Computing Curricula, Curriculum Guidelines for Undergraduate Degree Programs in Software Engineering, Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 2015.
- [5] Lethbridge T.C., What knowledge is important to a software professional?, *Computer (Long. Beach. Calif.)*, vol. 33, no. 5, pp. 44–50, 2000, doi: 10.1109/2.841783.
- [6] Exter M., Caskurlu S., and Fernandez T., Comparing computing professionals' perceptions of importance of skills and knowledge on the job and coverage in undergraduate experiences, *ACM Trans. Comput. Educ.*, vol. 18, no. 4, 2018, doi: 10.1145/3218430.
- [7] Garousi V., Giray G., Tüzün E., Catal C., and Felderer M., Aligning software engineering education with industrial needs: A meta-analysis, *J. Syst. Softw.*, vol. 156, pp. 65–83, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.jss.2019.06.044.
- [8] Gurcan F. and Kose C., Analysis of software engineering industry needs and trends: Implications for education, *Int. J. Eng. Educ.*, vol. 33, no. 4, pp. 1361–1368, 2017.
- [9] Stack Overflow Developer Survey 2019. <https://insights.stackoverflow.com/survey/2019#technology> (accessed Apr. 17, 2020).